

THE CONCEPT OF LOGICAL THINKING AND ITS CONCEPT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15212047>

Annotation: This article is dedicated to the study of the concept of logical thinking, as well as the analysis of its content and essence. The article examines the philosophical, psychological, and pedagogical aspects of logical thinking, its importance in everyday life, and its role in the education system. In addition, it discusses the development of logical thinking and its role in social and practical activities. The article offers scientifically grounded recommendations on methods and ways of developing logical thinking for students and learners.

Keywords: thinking, language, speech, logical thinking, sensation, perception, imagination, cognitive activity, understanding, hypothesis, thought, reasoning, idea, assumption, judgments.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена изучению понятия логического мышления, а также анализу его содержания и сущности. В статье рассматриваются философские, психологические и педагогические аспекты логического мышления, его значение в повседневной жизни и роль в системе образования. Кроме того, освещается развитие логического мышления и его роль в социальной и жизненной деятельности. Статья предлагает научно обоснованные рекомендации по методам и способам развития логического мышления для учащихся и студентов.

Ключевые слова: мышление, язык, речь, логическое мышление, ощущение, восприятие, представление, мыслительная деятельность, понимание, гипотеза, мысль, рассуждение, идея, предположение, суждения.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola mantiqiy tafakkur tushunchasini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, uning mazmuni va mohiyatini tahlil etadi. Maqolada mantiqiy tafakkurning falsafiy, psixologik va pedagogik jihatlari, uning kundalik hayotdagi ahamiyati va ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni keltirilgan. Shuningdek, mantiqiy tafakkurning rivojlanishi va uning ijtimoiy-hayotiy faoliyatdagi roli haqida ham so'z yuritiladi. i. Maqola o'quvchilarga va talabalar uchun mantiqiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish yo'llari va metodikalariga oid ilmiy asoslangan tavsiyalarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: tafakkur, til, nutq, mantiqiy tafakkur, sezgi, idrok, tasavvur, fikrlash faoliyati, tushunish, faraz qilish, fikr, mulohaza, g'oya, faraz, hukmlar.

Thinking is the highest form of mental activity of a person, the process of reflecting objective reality in consciousness. Since ancient times, it has been continuously studied as one of the main objects within the scope of philosophical, pedagogical, psychological, and physiological research. Thinking is a tool for understanding the surrounding environment, social phenomena, and reality, and it is also considered a primary condition for carrying out human activities. It is a high-level cognitive process that reflects reality more fully and precisely compared to sensations, perceptions, and imaginations. Thinking is a specific function of the human brain. Its neurophysiological basis consists of the interaction between the first and second signaling systems. During the process of tafakkur, thoughts, reasoning, ideas, hypotheses, and so on arise, and they are expressed in the form of concepts, judgments, and conclusions in the person's consciousness. Thinking is closely related to language and speech. The activity of thinking is manifested in the form of speech. During the communication process, not only does the emotional scope of a person's reflection expand, but also the acquired experience is shared with others. A person distinguishes himself from other beings by using his thinking, speech, and conscious behavior to determine the truth or falsity of the things and events he has perceived, imagined, or understood.

Through thinking, a person generalizes reality and directly (or indirectly) reflects it, understanding the most important connections, relationships, and characteristics between things and phenomena. Therefore, a person has the ability to predict the emergence, development, and consequences of social events and phenomena based on certain laws, patterns, and rules. Thinking is an object of study in many fields of science (philosophy, logic, sociology, pedagogy, physiology, cybernetics, biology). In psychology, thinking is classified into several types depending on the level of generalization of reality, the characteristics of problem-solving, the novelty of situations for the individual, and the level of activity of the person (sensory-motor, visual-figurative, practical, theoretical, voluntary, involuntary, abstract, creative, etc.). In social life, the educational process, and production, communication and relationships between people are also manifested through thinking. In a group, qualities of thinking such as critical reflection, self-criticism, evaluation, verification, self-checking, control, self-control, and group reasoning arise. The way a person perceives other individuals is also closely related to thinking. Creative work, discoveries, inventions, and suggestions are products of thinking. Psychology also examines the phylogenetic (related to the development of humanity) and

ontogenetic (related to the development of a person throughout their life) aspects of thinking. The complex issues of modern science demand a deeper study of the logical processes involved in thinking. Ancient Greek philosophers such as Aristotle, Democritus, Socrates, and Epicurus recognized thinking as the unity of the mind and perceptions, and were among the first to classify the laws and forms of thinking. Philosophers of the New Age, such as John Locke, Francis Bacon, C. Galvani, and David Hume, defined the manifestations of thinking as sensation, perception, imagination, and reflection.

In classical German philosophy (E. Kant, I. Fichte, F. Schelling, G. Hegel), thinking is manifested as a symbol of the subject's independence. German philosophers of the 18th century focused on the fact that thinking appears as a result of labor activity and social practice, taking on specific forms. It should be noted that in philosophical research, thinking primarily emerges as a social-historical process that realizes the cognitive possibilities of the individual. In the history of Western psychology, the study of thinking is acknowledged through the associative, behavioral, geshtalt psychology, and cognitive approaches as the main conceptual frameworks. Representatives of associative psychology (D. Hartley, J. Priestley, I. Tenn, G. Ebbinghaus, W. Wundt) view thinking as a process generated by the associative connection between past experiences and existing sensory experience, rejecting the creative synthesis of knowledge as one of its functions and not going beyond the subjective world and the world of ideas as the main and only objects of cognition. In the history of psychology, representatives of the Würzburg school (A. Külpe, A. Mayer, N. Ach, K. Bühler, K. Taylor) attempted to experimentally study thinking. In contrast to the associative theory, they showed that thinking has ordered directed characteristics and demonstrated the crucial importance of thinking in expressing the individual's personality through the process of reflection. Additionally, representatives of behaviorism, geshtalt psychology, and psychoanalysis (B. Skinner, A. Bandura, Z. Freud, A. K. Jung) researched various manifestations of thinking as phenomena within their teachings and substantiated their viewpoints.

In conclusion, in psychology, thinking is studied based on the degree of generalization of reality, the characteristics of problem-solving methods, the novelty of situations for the person, and the level of personal activity. Accordingly, it is classified into several types, such as sensory-motor, visual-figurative, practical, theoretical, voluntary, involuntary, abstract, creative thinking, and others. Thinking is the highest form of mental activity, a process

through which objective reality is reflected in the human mind. It serves as a means of understanding the environment, social phenomena, and reality, and is considered a fundamental condition for carrying out human activity. Compared to sensation, perception, and imagination, thinking is a higher cognitive process that reflects reality more fully and accurately. Thinking is a specific function of the human brain. Its neurophysiological foundation lies in the interaction between the first and second signaling systems. In the thinking process, thoughts, judgments, ideas, and hypotheses arise and are expressed in the mind in the form of concepts, propositions, and conclusions. Thinking is closely related to language and speech. Cognitive activity is manifested in speech. During verbal communication, not only is a person's emotional and reflective scope expanded, but the acquired experience is also shared with others. A human being is distinguished from other living creatures by their ability to think, speak, and act consciously. Through the act of thinking, a person determines the truth or falsehood of perceived, understood, and imagined objects and phenomena. By means of thinking, a person generalizes reality and reflects it indirectly, grasping the essential relationships, interactions, and properties of things and events. Thus, based on certain laws, patterns, and principles, a person gains the ability to foresee the emergence, development, and consequences of social events and phenomena.

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